

UNCERTAIN PAST TENSE IN THE TRANSLATION OF UZBEK ARTISTIC WORKS INTO CHINESE

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Abstract: *In this article, in the Chinese translation of past tense forms in the work of the Uzbek writer Utkir Hashimov, "The Affairs of the world", the suffix 过 (guò) is used. The characteristics of the expression of the past tense: -di, -gan, -gan edi, edi ekan, -ar edi are considered.*

Keywords: *suffix, indefinite past tense, tense category, verb forms, stative syntagma*

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada o'zbek yozuvchisi O'tkir Hoshimovning "Dunyoning ishlari" asarida -di, -gan, -gan edi, -di ekan, -ar edi kabi o'tgan zamon shakllarining xitoy tiliga noaniq o'tgan zamoni yasovchi 过 (guò) suffiksi orqali tarjima qilinishi hamda uning ifodalanish xususiyatlari tahlil etiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *suffiks, noaniq o'tgan zamon, zamon kategoriyasi, fe'l shakllari, turg'un sintagma*

Аннотация: *В данной статье анализируются особенности перевода прошедших временных форм, таких как -di, -gan, -gan edi, -di ekan, -ar edi, использованных узбекским писателем Уткиром Хошимовым в его произведении "Дела земные", в контексте китайского языка с использованием суффикса 过 (guò), а также рассматриваются особенности его выражения.*

Ключевые слова: *суффикс, неопределенное прошедшее время, категория времени, глагольные формы, статическая синтагма.*

We know that in the process of translating Uzbek works of art into Eastern languages, especially Chinese, there are unique difficulties. The main reason for this is not only the uniqueness of the mentality, traditions, and cultural values of the Uzbek nation but also the fundamental difference in grammar between the Uzbek and Chinese languages, which causes major difficulties. In particular, it is quite a complicated process to correctly reflect the tense categories given in Uzbek artistic works in the Chinese language.

Although many works are devoted to the past tense system of the Uzbek language, we should note that it has not yet sufficiently developed this problem. Different authors distinguish a different number of past tense forms in the Uzbek language. From: A. Kh. Sulaimanov [1, 3] based on the way of forming the past tense, twenty-two tenses distinguish the form: -di, - (i) bdi, -gan, -gan edi, -ar edi, -

(i) b edi, -moqda edi, -moqchi edi, -bormoqchi edi, -gan ekan, -gan emish, -gan bo‘ldi, -di ekan, -a(y) degan bo‘ldi, -ib oldi, -gandas bo‘ldi, - gan bo‘lsa kerak , -sa bo‘lsa kerak, -gisi keldi, -sa bo‘ladimi, -ay deb qoldi, -gan bo‘lmasin, -magan bo‘lsa edi, -(i)sh bilan bo‘ldi, -(a)y dedi, -(i))shi kerak edi. It is easy to see that this classification of past tense verb forms with multi-level division is very awkward in practice.

E.D. Polivanov [2, 65,87-88] distinguishes six tenses in the Uzbek language: simple past with and five complex past a) a) –gan (bergan) bilan kelgan tarixiy o‘tgan va –gan edi (bergan edi) historical past; b) –gan bilan kelgan egalik affiksi (berganim bor) this form consisting of an adjective combined with the possessive affix with "I have given"; v) the perfect form comes with participle: ib bilan kelgan (beribdi) perfekt; g) –ib edi (borib edi) comes with +perfekt; d) -ar va -r (berar edi).

A.G. Ghulamov "Verb" [3, 88] also highlighted in his work. After all, unlike E.D. Polivanov, A.G. Gulomov use new terms. He notes six types of past tenses: past definite, past perfect, past subjective, past continuous tenses. A.N. Kononov gives eight tense systems, to which, in addition to the forms listed by E.D. Polivanov and A.G. Gulomov, he adds a certain definite imperfection ("yozmoqda edim" I was writing) and a long past tense (I was writing) [4, 215-228]. A. Khojiyev distinguishes three forms of the simple past tense (forms with past verbs: (-di, -gan, -ib) and seven complex past tense forms with the verb edi [5; 476]. Such conflicting types of classification can cause difficulties in choosing the correct Chinese equivalent in the process of translating Uzbek works of art.

In our article, the features of the expression of the past indefinite tense through the auxiliary word 过 guò in the Chinese translation of the work of the sharp Uzbek writer O'tkir Hashimov "Works of the World". In particular, we can witness that the past tense forms: -gan, -gan edi, -ar edi, edi ekan, -di are translated into Chinese using the suffix 过 guò. They form the Past Indefinite Tense using the suffix 过 guò to show that the action happened one or more times in the indefinite past tense. The suffix 过 guò can be used only with pure (both restitutive and result-oriented) verbs.

So, the action combined with the suffix 过 guò means an action that happened in the past in an indefinite tense and has no direct connection with the present time or the time in question. It is also used to report or clarify that an action or a certain situation happened at least once in the past with a certain person somewhere.

Shuyam **qarg’agan edi** deydi

He also says that he cursed [6, 186]

说你以前**咒过**他 [7, 157]

Shuō nǐ yǐqián zhòuguò tā

The Uzbek long-past verb form is combined with the Chinese verb 咒 zhòu "to crow" through the form of the suffix 过 guò, expressing an action that took place in the indefinite long past. is coming

Qorong'i osmonda yana ham qoraroq soaydek qilt etmay turgan bu qoyalar bizga o'xshaganlarning necha-nechasini **ko'rdi ekan**?... [6, 9]. How many of those like us did these rocks, standing like an even blacker sun in the dark sky, see?... [6, 9]

午夜时分黑暗的夜色中这些大山见**过**了多少人的悲欢离合啊 [7, 13]. Zài wǔyè shífēn hēi'àn de yèsè zhōng zhèxiē dàshān jiànguòle duōshǎo rén de bēihuānlíhé a...

The verb in the Uzbek sentence given above is given in the form, which represents the long past tense, and is translated into Chinese using the suffix 过 guò and 了 le.

Ilgarilari bir haqiqatni **bilardim**. Ona uchun bolaning katta-kichigi bo'lmaydi [6, 8]. I used to know the truth. For the mother, the child is not big or small [6, 8]

以前听说过不管孩子的年龄多大, 在妈妈眼里永远都是孩子, 是在这个世界上要保护的**宝宝** [7, 11]

Yìqián tīng shuōguò bu guǎn háizi de niánlíng duōdà, zài māmā yǎn lǐ yǒngyuǎn dōu shì háizi, shì zài zhège shìjiè shàng yào bǎohù de bǎobǎo

This sentence belongs to the indefinite imperfect tense in Uzbek, and the verb "to know" is expressed through the form, and it means that the action took place in a long indefinite tense. Translated into Chinese as 听说 tīng shuō "as they say", it also served to express the past subjective tense.

Uniyam ayt**gansiz**-ku [6, 12]

You said that too [6, 12]

这个故事**你**已经讲过了啊 [7,7] Zhège gùshì nǐ yǐjīng jiǎngguòle a?

Because of the addition of the suffix 过 guò, the verb 讲 jiǎng "to tell", in the example gives the meaning of the Uzbek past perfect tense form "told" with past tense. We assume that the action has "already" taken place, and there is a possibility to continue or repeat this action in the future. In addition, the verb with the suffix 过 guò does not tell about the current state of the subject at the time of speech, but also about an action that has been completed up to the time of speech and can be continued or repeated.

Unlike the 了 le suffix, the 过 guò suffix can express both a one-time action and an action repeated several times in a sentence, and can be used together with the continuous tense. For example:

Rahmatullaga (unga) aytuv**dim**-a tog'angning qizini ol deb... [6, 71]

I told Rahmatullah (him) to take your uncle's daughter... [6, 71]

我跟**儿子**说过好几次, 让他跟**她**的表妹结婚... [7, 73]

Wǒ gēn er zi shuōguò hǎojǐ cì, ràng tā gēn tā de biǎomèi jiéhūn...

The past indefinite tense is often called a multiple type, but, as A.A.Dragunov points out, the verb in this tense is a count word with a number, and 一 yī is a count word that indicates a one-time action. For example:

Hoji buvining ko'zlarida, hamisha ma'yuz boquvchi ko'zlarida chog' yaraqlab ketgandek bo'ldi [6, 75]

In the eyes of Haji's grandmother, and in the eyes of the ever-gloomy breadwinner, it seemed as if the snow had split [6, 75]

但豪吉奶奶的目光中却闪过一丝愉快 [7, 76]

Dàn háo jí nǎinai de mùguāng zhōng què shǎnguò yīsī yúkuài

In cases where the action happened in the past (if it was not clearly indicated), the indefinite imperfect tense in Uzbek corresponds to the indefinite past tense in Chinese.

The negative form of the past indefinite tense is formed using the negative 没 méi (没有 méiyǒu) like the past perfect tense. But the suffix 过 guò in the negative form remains méiláiguòméi láiguò "didn't come".

The negative form of the past indefinite tense completely denies the existence of an action in the past, indicating that the action never happened, never existed until now; it has a more generalized, absolute character and, if necessary, gives the meaning of the Uzbek words "never until now", "never before" and so on. The negative form of the past indefinite is often combined with the adverb 从来 cónglái "never yet" and various words that emphasize time duration or strict negation, for example:

Bittayam kasal bo'lmagan [6, 58]

Not one patient [6, 58]

一次病也没生过 [7, 62]

Yīcì bìng yě méi shēngguò

In the Uzbek language, the indefinite past tense sentence made with the definite negative form is expressed in the Chinese language by the fixed phrase “一次+noun 也没+verb+过”.

In conclusion, we can give the following:

- The past tense formed using Uzbek verb forms: -di, -gan, -gan edi, -di ekan, -ar edi can be expressed by the suffix 过 guò in Chinese;

- The negative form of the suffix 过 guò is formed by 没/没有 méi/méiyǒu and the corresponding stable constructions made with it. In this he expresses a firm denial;

- Sentences with the suffix "过 guò" include tenses of different times, which emphasize the fact that the action took place in the distant past.

- It is appropriate to translate the sentence with the help of this suffix based on the meaning of the context.

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